

DESIGN OF TRANSVERSE BIAXIAL TENSILE TESTS ON CRUCIFORM SPECIMENS

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1 Introduction

The particular case of the mechanism of damage known as inter-fiber or matrix failure under transverse tension has already been the object of several micromechanical studies by the authors [1]. These studies have made it possible to understand the initiation of failure at the micromechanical scale as well as its later progress, which leads to the macro-failure of the material.

Many of the existing proposals for the prediction of the inter-fiber failure at lamina level are based on the hypothesis that the failure taking place at a plane is governed by the components of the stress vector associated to that plane. This assumption has been revised by París et al [2] and Correa et al [3] for the tension dominated matrix failure by means of single-fiber Boundary Element models subjected to biaxial loading.

The results obtained showed that the presence of a secondary tensile load could alter several aspects of the micromechanical stages of damage growth already detected for the tension uniaxial case leading to the conclusion that the presence of this out of plane stress component could slightly delay the generation of failure.

The authors of this work consider essential to check the validity of the conclusions derived from the aforementioned numerical micromechanical studies by means of macromechanical experimental tests. To this end, tension-tension biaxial tests have been planned and designed.

The cost of biaxial tests is considerably higher than the uniaxial ones due to the complexity of the biaxial testing machines. Different solutions have been historically proposed for performing biaxial test in uniaxial testing machines. The present work is a continuation of the investigation presented in [4], where the design and manufacturing of a new device

to carry out biaxial tests in uniaxial testing machines, was described.

The first part of the investigation presented in this contribution is connected to the development of virtual testing by FEM. The results of these analyses are used to assess the design of the adequate geometry of the cruciform specimens to be tested. In particular, Finite Element models have been developed in order to design a cruciform specimen that minimizes the effect of stress concentrations for the case of unidirectional laminates tested under bi-directional transverse loads.

The second part of the investigation deals with the manufacturing of cruciform specimens, aiming to minimize the presence of defects, as well as their biaxial testing in the already manufactured device.

2 Design of the cruciform specimen

2.1 Model

To avoid premature failure of the specimen outside the zone of interest it is necessary to perform a preliminary design of the cruciform specimen to be tested under tension-tension biaxial loading. There exists a considerable amount of studies in literature about cruciform specimens, both for metals and fiber reinforced laminates, though it is not easy to find a specific design for unidirectional laminates to be subjected to transverse loads (i.e. 90° specimens).

The design of the specimen suitable for biaxial transverse load testing is based on a main objective: it must assure that the failure takes place at the central zone of the specimen (the area really subjected to biaxial load); besides, stresses at this zone should be uniform and cover a wide enough area. Additionally, geometrical features should not promote or increase undesirable effects such as stress concentrations.

Fig. 1. Types of specimen considered.

Fig. 2. Example of a) geometrical model, b) FEM model. (Type C specimen).

Following the aforementioned premises four different geometries have been initially considered (specimen types A, B, C and D, Fig. 1) and Finite

Element models designed based on them in order to analyze the stress state occurring when subjecting them to tension-tension biaxial load.

Figure 3. σ_{xx} distribution (T-T case).

The four geometries chosen are composed by a main body, which represents the cruciform specimen itself manufactured from a unidirectional laminate, and 8 reinforcing tabs (one at each side of each “arm” of the specimen). These tabs pursue a double function: first, the assurance of the adequate fixing of the specimen to the machine grips during testing, and second, a thickness increase of the specimen out of the zone of interest, in order to promote failure initiation at the biaxial loading (central) zone of the specimen. The first three types of specimen use just one curvature radius defining the central zone ($R=1.5$ mm, $R=6.25$ mm, and $R=19.97$ mm, respectively), whereas the fourth one employs two different radii. Geometrical specifications of the four specimens are detailed in Fig. 4. It is important to point out that the later specimens manufacturing process also needs to be considered in the final

design of the specimen. In this particular case, the 90° orientation of the laminate is one of the critical features to be taken into account. The unidirectional laminate considered corresponds to a carbon-epoxy system (AS4/3501-6) whereas tabs are thought to be manufactured from glass fiber +45/-45 fabric. Due to the symmetry shown by the four specimens considered only an eighth has been modeled for the FEM analyses, by using the adequate boundary conditions. Different loading cases have been considered, all of them corresponding to a fixed value, σ_0 , of the external tension applied at the edge of the horizontal arm of the specimen (x axis) and different portions of σ_0 (characterized by a coefficient $n=0.25, 0.5, 0.75$ and 1) at the edge of the vertical one (y axis). σ_0 has been taken equal to the tensile strength associated to the laminate considered,

48 MPa in this case. The scheme of the problem described can be consulted in Fig. 2a for Type C specimen, where a view of the mesh employed can also be observed (Fig. 2b).

2.2 First results

The stress state associated to the different loading cases considered has been analyzed for each type of specimen. Focusing our attention on the tension-tension (T-T) case ($n=1$) the results show that σ_{xx} and σ_{yy} are the dominant stresses, showing in fact identical distributions.

σ_{xx} distributions are shown in Fig. 6, where a zoom of the central zone is included. For comparison purposes the same scale of representation has been used for all cases, extending from the maximum tensile value obtained (occurring at type A specimen) to the maximum compressive value (occurring at type D specimen). Stress concentrations are found for the four specimens at the free edge, the maximum value occurring for type B (290 MPa) followed by types D (205 MPa), A (160 MPa) and C (149 MPa). Tensile values are found at all points of the central zone as well as the horizontal arm of the specimens, whereas very small (almost negligible) compressive values appear at the vertical arm of the specimens.

Looking at type A specimen, a uniform σ_{xx} distribution is detected at its central zone though its value being just a 25% of the maximum tension encountered at the free edge. Besides, higher tensions are also vertically distributed along the horizontal tab border, which would eventually lead to a failure out of the biaxial zone. The use of a higher curvature radius, type B specimen, reduces the difference existing between σ_{xx} values at the central zone and the maximum σ_{xx} at the free edge, though still being quite significant (43%). Higher tensions are also distributed vertically along the horizontal tab border but extending to part of the central zone in this case.

With reference to σ_{xx} distribution associated to type C specimen, this is very similar to than shown by type B though the stress concentration, and thus the maximum tensile value, moves towards the horizontal arm. Besides, the stress value at the centre of the specimen is only a 36% of this maximum. Finally, type D specimen presents a relation between

σ_{xx} value associated to the centre of the specimen and maximum σ_{xx} similar to that already encountered for type B specimen (42%); high σ_{xx} values are also found at the biaxial zone though not reaching the center of the specimen. The described results lead to the discarding of types A and C. Additional results obtained for types B and D specimens associated to the remaining loading cases ($n=0.25, 0.5, 0.75$) point to type D as the best design, since, for those cases and excepting the stress concentration, the aforementioned high σ_{xx} lateral area, occupies the whole biaxial zone. Anyway, the difference between the stress concentration at the free edge and σ_{xx} value at the centre of the specimen is still quite significant, leading then to think in a necessary modification of type D geometry.

2.3 Geometrical modifications

The first geometrical modification developed is shown in Fig. 7 (type M1 specimen) and consists in limiting the reduced thickness area just to the central zone of the specimen. Besides the specimens are now manufactured as an entire body made of unidirectional carbon-epoxy laminate. This modification is intended to minimize the effect of the stress concentration at the free edge and promote failure initiation at the central zone.

Fig. 4. Type M1 specimen.

The results presented in Fig. 5 show that the free edge stress concentration is still present although its value (108 MPa) is substantially lower than that associated to Type D specimen (205 MPa). Besides, the stress state at the central zone is more uniform

than in the previous specimens and σ_{xx} value at the centre of the specimen reaches in this case a 68% of the maximum value. This maximum is located both at the free edge and at the boundary of the central zone, probably associated to the local geometry of the specimen. Fig. 5 shows the distribution of σ_{xx} , for the M1 specimen under traction-traction (T-T) load.

Fig. 5. σ_{xx} distribution associated to T-T case. (M1 specimen)

Thus, the geometrical modification implemented in Type M1 specimen supposes an approach to the final objective but still seems insufficient. Subsequent modifications lead to Type M3 specimen, shown in Fig. 6. The central zone of this specimen is now elliptical and maintains the thickness of Type M1; instead, the outer areas of the specimen have increased their thickness from 1.5 in M1 to 2.5 in M3.

Fig. 6. Type M3 specimen.

Fig. 7. σ_{xx} distribution associated to T-T case. (M3 specimen)

Figure 7 shows σ_{xx} distribution for the particular case of traction-traction (T-T) acting on Type M3 specimen. The results show significant improvements with reference to the previous models. The central zone of the specimen is now quite uniformly stressed, with values of about an 86% of the maximum. This maximum is detected at the edge of this central zone instead at the outer side of the specimen. Unfortunately, an undesirable and unavoidable concentration area of slightly lower values is still detected in the outer side of the specimen.

3 Design and manufacturing of the biaxial device

A literature review was performed previously to the new proposal made in this work. Hoferlin [5] used independent actuators for each loading axis. In the group of proposals using a device in single axis machines, Ferron and Mankinde [6] made a tension-tension fixture, analogous to that proposed by Tasan [7]. Fraunhofer [8] also proposed a simpler (less mechanical links) tension-tension device. See also Bhatnagar [9] with a device allowing non-equibiaxial tension. The device designed in this work allows tension-tension (also compression-compression) tests, see Fig.8, using cruciform specimens, and tension-compression tests, see Fig.9, using standard samples with variable loading ratio.

Fig. 8. Device set-up for tension-tension tests.

The two lateral columns represent the characteristic load frame clearance of an INSTRON 4481.

The device has been designed to be used up to a maximum compression load, measured in the load cell of the uniaxial testing machine, of 20KN.

Fig. 9. Set-up for tension-compression tests.

Three different load transfer systems (from the device to the sample) were investigated. A first using rigid grips, demonstrated not to give a good alignment, and also to be very tedious in the setup process. A second one, using flexible steel wires, in order to get a self-alignment effect, also showed not to be effective nor easy to use. A third attempt was made with rigid rings, also with self-alignment effect and much more easy to use. This third option

was the one chosen for the tests and it is shown in Fig.10. In the material configuration under test (the fiber direction perpendicular to the sample plane), this loading transmission system was possible due to the relatively low strength of the sample, but needed the use of tabs, as shown in Fig.10.

Fig. 10. Load transmission system using rigid rings.

4 Manufacturing of the cruciform sample

A special feature of the test covered in this work is the particular fiber orientation (perpendicular to the sample plane), which made the manufacturing of the samples also particular. Two very thick laminates creating a cross were bonded/cured using four aluminium blocks, see Fig.11.

Fig. 11. Curing of the piece form which the cruciform samples will be obtained.

From the same block (Fig.11) slices were cut and then lateral surfaces machined using as a master copy a metallic sample which was machined to the shape described in Section 2 using numerical control. Then, polishing of the top and bottom

surfaces and bonding of tabs at the end of each arm was carried out.

Fig. 12. Samples before tab bonding and strain gages installation.

5 Results

The device has been used to carry out tension-tension tests with variable ratio on cruciform specimens of composite materials with the fiber direction in the plane perpendicular to the specimen. Special care has been devoted in controlling the bending parameter in both loading axes. Monitoring of this bending parameter (measured following ASTM E1012 standard) has been performed by means of strain gages at both sides of the specimen and both loading directions.

Fig. 12 shows the value of the bending parameter, for both loading axes during the test of sample No.18. As in this work the influence of the biaxiality is under analysis, it is important to guarantee a satisfactory bending parameter at the instant of

failure. Nevertheless, it can be observed in Fig. 13, the value of the bending parameter is below 5% almost for the entire test, and specially low (1% or 2%) at failure.

Fig. 14 shows one sample after failure, the details of the strain gage and failure path can be clearly observed. The sample in Fig. 14 corresponds to a double radius sample with uniform thickness (type D specimen).

Fig. 14. Failure of a sample.

Fig. 15 shows the summary of results for all tension-tension tests on cruciform specimens with double radius and constant thickness (type D specimen).

Fig. 13. Bending parameter during the test.

Fig. 15. Results for the tension-tension tests in cruciform specimens.

The stress at the fillet radius is plotted vs the stress ratio (n_σ) at the center of the sample. The value of the stress ratio in a uniaxial test (obtained using the strain gages data and the 2D constitutive law in generalized plane stress) is around $n_\sigma = -0.3$ due to the geometry of the sample.

With this reference value, the rest of variable stress ratio loading tests, varying from $0.6 < n_\sigma < 1$ are shown in Fig. 15. Although the results show a high dispersion, all tests have shown an excellent behavior in terms of the bending parameter, which validates the use of the designed biaxial device and allows a more extensive test program to be carried out at a reasonably low cost, with full confidence in the experimental results.

6 Conclusions

FEM virtual testing has been used to assess the appropriate geometry of a cruciform specimen suitable for tension-tension transverse tests.

A device for performing biaxial tests in uniaxial machines has been conceived and manufactured.

Manufacturing of the cruciform specimens as well as preliminary tension-tension tests, with variable loading ratio, have been performed.

The manufactured device has shown an excellent behavior in terms of the bending parameter and has allowed the loading ratio to be modified.

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